

Original Research Article

Effect Assessment of Human Immunodeficiency Virus co infection on Serum Level of Cytokines and Chemokines of Multidrug Resistant-tuberculosis Patients in Tanzania

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Abstract

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Multidrug-resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB) with human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) immunologic state which is marked by chemokine and cytokine distortion is indicated by boosting the defense stimulation to a patient. The effect of coexisting infections on the MDR-TB patient with HIV is still not fully explored, hence this study aims to assess the serum level of chemokine/cytokine indices in MDR-TB patients with HIV or without HIV infection. We assessed serum levels of chemokines and cytokines from 92 MDR-TB patients with HIV and 106 MDR-TB patients without HIV before initiation of treatment and after six months of treatment with second-line anti-TB plus ARV drugs and MDR-TB without HIV with second-line anti TB drugs applying Luminex assay to assess the effect of HIV on serum level of cytokines and chemokines of MDR-TB patients before and after initiation of intensive second-line anti TB treatment for MDR-TB and second line anti TB plus ARV drugs for MDR-TB with HIV infection. The proportion of IFN- γ /IL-4 and IFN- γ /IL-10 indicated by a notable elevation following medication in MDR-TB patients without HIV but not in MDR-TB patients with HIV which might point to extended harm of defense reaction to MDR-TB patients with HIV as contrasted to MDR-TB patients without HIV. The mid serum level of MCP-3, MIP-1 β , IP-10, IFN- γ , and IL-4, was notably dissimilar ($p < 0.01$) ahead and following medication in the mentioned two groups of patients above. There was no notable variation between MDR-TB patients with HIV and MDR-TB patients without HIV ($p > 0.01$) in the serum level of any of the chemokines or cytokines ahead of initiation of medicament and second line anti TB drug therapy did not alter the level of any of the assessed cytokines in MDR-TB patients with HIV. From the assessment of this study, second-line anti TB therapy notably improves the Th1 mediators and level of chemokines but does not restore the protection reaction in MDR-TB patients with HIV. MDR-TB patients with HIV or MDR-TB patients without HIV display related serum levels of cytokine and chemokine design.

Keywords: Chemokine, Cytokines, HIV/AIDS, MDR-TB

INTRODUCTION

The syndicate of Multidrug-resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB) and human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) pose a health threat to the community (Weerawat et al., 2016; Boggiano et al., 2017). Several roles in the protection and pathological responses in MDR-TB are the key roles of cytokines and chemokines in MDR-TB patients, tumor

necrosis factor (TNF- α) and interleukin -10 (IL-10), interferon-gamma (IFN- γ) take part in a vital role of anti-TB cell-mediated defense (Adrian, et al, 2015; Domingo et al., 2016; Eldholm et al., 2016). No matter even having a normal CD4+ cell count a patient having HIV infection has an immense risk of contracting TB (Mikhael et al.,

2018). There are so many factors participating in this proliferated risk of contracting TB, which include, diminished CD4+ T-cell count, an extended period of HIV-infection to a patient, and also the shortage of ART drugs in the facility. (Fatima and Nabeela, 2016; Martino et al., 2019).

The TNF- α and IFN- γ are the major cytokines mediators in granuloma formation that curb tuberculosis (TB) infection; on the other hand, pro-inflammatory cytokines and especially TNF- α will, in excess lead the way to drastic tissue demolition and necrosis jellification (Sharma, et al., 2005). The endured containment of secured latent tuberculosis infection (LTBI) is based on the balance between protective responses (pro-inflammatory) and suppressive responses (anti-inflammatory) to restrict immunopathology (Cardona P and Cardona PJ, 2019). The dominant Th1 cell activation is under the regulation of other T-cell subsets. IL-4, IL10 and IL-13 are secreted by polarized Th2 sets and thereby hamper the Th1-mediated pro-inflammatory and tissue devastating response. CD4+CD25+ regulatory T-cells favor Th2 skewing by augmenting suppressive reactions and promoting negative feedback on Th1 cells. (Guyot et al., 2006). Regulatory T cells are enlarged in blood and disease position in tuberculosis patients. Secretion of IL-4 in active TB patients has always been looked at as a marker of Th2 cell action (Kidd P, 2003). There is a confirmation that increased IL-4 emission enhances TNF- α toxicity and fibrosis (Hernandez et al., 2003), and promotes TNF- α mediated apoptosis in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (Mtb) activated lymphocytes. IL-4 is hence involved in the immunopathology of TB infection (Seah GT, Rook GA, 2006), and its existence has been associated with the extent of tuberculosis disease (Ordway et al., 2005; Dheda et al., 2005; Seah GT, Rook GA, 2001). In the case of concurrent HIV and Mtb infection the IL-4/ TNF- α interaction could aggravate the situation, as the depletion of T-cells would make the host vulnerable to HIV development.

For the improvement and development of new diagnostics and treatment standards, it is very important to know the composition of the defense protection to TB (Reiser and Banerjee, 2016). To know the protection of TB infection and illness, some indices are required to be considered, which comprise the HIV condition, duration of the HIV to patients, and accessibility of ARV drugs (Mikhael et al: 2018). An intensive study has been done on cytokines reaction with the dissimilar outcome on each situation of the disease according to genetic settings (Mikhael and Atadzhan, 2018; Barham et al., 2019). Unfortunately HIV- TB co-infection pathogenesis is not well understood, but it is believed that cytokines and chemokines play a great role in enhancing defense and bring protection during therapy (Shankar et al., 2014; Fatima and, Nabeela, 2016; Riti et al., 2020). Diminished protection and HIV viral load in subsequent therapy of opportunistic infections in addition to TB are well familiar

in the realm of health care (Shankar et al., 2014). TB therapy on the cytokines and chemokines level along with HIV-infected adults with MDR-TB is inadequately studied, (Shankar et al., 2014; Chem, Hout and Hope, 2019) whereas in different researches it has dissimilar outcome (Morris et al., 2003; Karo et al., 2017). From the different reports on studies done previously, it indicates a decline of defense mechanisms without a change in viral load (Mahan, et al., 2014). Mihret and colleagues in 2012 they announced that "anti TB medication changed the chemokines and cytokines levels in patients with TB without HIV infection" (Mahan et al., 2014).

In this study we have worked in a similar panel of chemokines and cytokines to investigate the assumption to check the diversity along with the defense in reaction before medication with second-line anti-TB plus ARV drugs in MDR-TB patients with HIV compared to MDR-TB patients without HIV, hence we worked on unquickened serum samples with the assumption it will reflect the systemic foundation and reflects the systemic immune response to see the protection reaction in MDR-TB patients with HIV and MDR-TB patients without HIV and for observation of anti-TB medication outcome in both groups.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design and study area

This was a descriptive follow-up study, conducted from May 2017 to October 2019 in Kibong'oto Infectious Diseases Hospital (KIDH) in Siha District, Northern Tanzania with a 340-bed capacity. The hospital provides long-term hospitalization and provides all drugs required for the treatment of MDR-TB. KIDH receives all MDR-TB patients for treatment from all parts of Tanzania as referred cases, it also houses a major HIV care and treatment support Centre (CTC).

Study population

We recruited 198 patients with active confirmed MDR-TB, out of the enrolled patients, 92 patients had HIV positive and 106 patients had MDR-TB without HIV. The patients signed an informed consent form.

Sample Size Determination and Sampling Technique

A time-bound consecutive sampling method was applied to enlist the research clients from the previous research. All were established MDR-TB patients by Gene Xpert, line probe assay and DST (Angeby KAK, Klintz L, 2002; Morgan et al., 2005; Ling and Zwerling, 2008; P.Ioannidis et al., 2011; Reddy and Alvarez-Uria, 2017) who were

referred to KIDH in course of the research time of May to October 2019 were enlisted in this research consecutively.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Patients included in the research were those established to be MDR-TB with HIV and MDR-TB without HIV and who have consented to partake in the research aged 18 years and above. Clients who met all the inclusion criteria but not Tanzanian residents were excluded from the research and those who have started medication before the research also were excluded. The Multiplex Map Kit (Merck Millipore, Darmstadt, Germany) was utilized to assess dissimilar human cytokines and chemokines, under the guidance of the producer's directive.

Multiplex investigation

Blood specimens were gathered up from every client in clean test tubes twice. The first specimen at enrollment and the second specimen following the finalization of intensive second line anti TB drug medication. Serum was differentiated by spinning at 1000 rpm for five minutes and kept at -20°C awaiting the multiplex assessment.

We used a 17plex kit IL-1, IL-4, IL-7, IL-9, IL 10, IL-12, IL-17, fractalkine (Epidermal Growth Factor (EGF), IFN- γ , Granulocyte-Macrophage Colony Stimulating Factor (GM-CSF), IFN- γ inducible protein (IP-10 /CXCL-10), MCP-3, Macrophage Chemoattractant Protein 1 (MCP- 1/CXCL), Monocyte Inflammatory Protein 1 β (MIP-1 β), TNF and Vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) from Germany-Merck Millipore and numerous cytokine assessment was executed utilizing Luminex (Germany-Merck Millipore) technology. The assays were executed by applying the producer's directives on the Luminex platform.

Ethical considerations

Through the Kilimanjaro Christian Medical University College Research and Ethical Review Committee (CRERC) the ethical clearance was acquired. Authorization through KIDH officials to run the study was also procured.

Statistical Analysis

Data exploration

To explore the data in this study the Luminex® 100 IS, software version 2.3.182 was applied. The Human Cyto-

kine Quality Controls I and ii which were used in the assessment as low and high concentration quality controls and background (empty) sequentially plus Assay buffer were incorporated in the kit. To identify the continuance of the standard curve, six non zero standard points covering from 3.2 pg/ml to 10 000 pg/ml were assayed in duplicate to generate a standard curve and the correlation coefficient (R²) was computed in every investigation.

Statistical analysis

Simple frequencies, descriptive assessment, and the allocation of outcomes were assessed. The data were computed utilizing Graph pad prism software, version 4.0. Data were log changed to standardize its location. To examine the importance of the detected dissimilarity in every variable in MDR-TB patients with HIV and MDR-TB patients without HIV. Non-parametric Mann-Whitney U tests were executed.

RESULTS

In the current study, 198 patients who were assessed for biochemical, hematological, and immunological indices (CD4) were enrolled. hence we assessed the level of serum cytokines and chemokines to the same patients as a continuation study The patients were confirmed MDR-TB referred to KIDH of which 92(46.46%) were MDR-TB patients with HIV and all were ART naïve with a mean CD4 count of 311 ± 14.9 cells/ μl . The mean age of MDR-TB patients without HIV was 28.5 ± 1.5 and 32.8 ± 1.4 respectively. (Table 1)

In the assessment of serum level of cytokines and chemokines on MDR-TB patients, we established that the mid serum level of the cytokines and chemokines assessed was not affected by HIV status even though the MDR-TB patients with HIV have a bit elevated level on the whole of the cytokines and chemokines mediators (Figure 1).

On the inquiry of serum level of chemokines and cytokines, we assessed the serum level of the chemokines and cytokines following 6 months of the intensive phase of second-line anti-TB medication to assess if any of these cytokines along with chemokines will reveal a diversity among MDR-TB with HIV and MDR-TB patients without HIV as a result of second-line anti-TB medication. We established that the median level of IFN- γ , IL-4, IP-10, MCP-3, and MIP-1 β were statistically dissimilar ($p < 0.01$) following medication in MDR-TB patients without HIV but not in MDR-TB patients with HIV ($p > 0.01$) (Figure 2). The median serum level of IL-4 and IP-10 was notably diminished while the level of IFN- γ , MCP-3, and MIP-1 β was notably raised following medication in HIV negative dropped TB patients. Finally,

Table 1. Social demographic Details of Multidrug-Resistant Tuberculosis patients (n=198)

Characteristics	Number	%
Age levels in years		
20-30	58	29.30
31-40	76	38.38
41 -50	60	30.30
> 50	4	2.02
Formal education		
None	1	0.50
Primary school	158	79.80
Secondary school	29	14.65
Tertiary education	10	5.05
Gender		
Female	76	38.38
Male	122	61.62
Marital status		
Single	105	53.03
Married	93	46.97
HIV status		
MDR-TB with HIV	92	46.46
MDR-TB without HIV	106	53.54

Figure 1.(i). Epidermal Growth Factor (EGF) and Vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) were assessed before the initiation of second-line anti-TB medication. Normal ranges of VEGF are 62–707 pg/ml for serum

we assessed the proportion of Th1 (IFN- γ and IL-12 (p40)) and Th2 (IL-4 and IL-10) cytokines preliminary to the following medication. Nothing of the proportion of IFN- γ /IL-4, IFN γ /IL-10, IL-12(p40)/IL-4 and IL-12(p40)/IL-10 were notably unrelated within MDR-TB patients with HIV or MDR-TB patients without HIV

(Figure 2), while the serum concentration of IFN- γ /IL-4 and IFN- γ /IL-10 was notably elevated ($p < 0.01$) in MDR-TB patients with HIV than MDR-TB without HIV patients following medication (Figure 3).

Figure 1. (iv) Chemokines (IP-10, MCP-1, MCP-3, MIP-1, β , and fractalkine), assessed before medication.

Figure 1. (ii). Proinflammatory mediators: Interferon-gamma (IFN γ), Interleukin (IL) 12 (p 40), and Tumor necrosis factor (TNF) assessed before initiation of second-line anti-TB medication.

Figure 1.(iii). Anti-inflammatory mediators: Interleukin (IL)-10 and Interleukin (IL) – 4, assessed before the initiation of second-line anti-TB medication.

SERUM LEVEL OF IP-10, MCP-1, MCP-3, MIP-1, β , AND FRACTALKINE

Figure 1. (iv). Chemokines (IP-10, MCP-1, MCP-3, MIP-1, β , and fractalkine), assessed before medication. Horizontal lines point out the median of MDR-TB without HIV (packed circles) and MDR-TB with HIV (Unlocked circles). Uninduced serum specimens from MDR-TB patients with HIV (n=92) and MDR-TB patients without HIV (n=106) were assessed by Multiplex Cytokines. Investigation of data done by application of non-parametric Mann Whitney test with p-value showing notable variation following the change of data to Log10 values.

SERUM LEVEL OF EGF AND VEGF

Figure 2. (i) Epidermal Growth Factor (EGF) and Vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF). Assessed following 6 months of intensive treatment with second-line anti TB. Normal ranges of VEGF are 62–707 pg/ml for serum

Figure 2. (ii) Pro-inflammatory mediators: *interferon-gamma* (IFN- γ , *interleukin* (IL) 12 (p40), and Tumor necrotic factor (TNF). Assessed following 6 months of intensive treatment with second-line anti TB drugs.

Figure 2.(iii) Anti-inflammatory mediators: *interleukin* (IL)-10 and *interleukin* (IL) -4. Assessed following 6 months of intensive treatment with second-line anti TB drugs.

SERUM LEVEL OF IP 10, MCP 1, MCP 3, MIP 1 AND FRACTALKINE

Figure 2. (iv). Chemokines (MIP-1 β and fractalkine, IP-10, MCP-1, MCP-3). Horizontal lines show mid of MDR-TB patients with HIV ahead of medication (packed circles). MDR-TB patients without HIV following medication (packed triangle). MDR-TB patients with HIV ahead of medication (packed by tart shape) and MDR-TB patients without HIV following medication (packed by the upturned triangle).

Th1/Th2 PROPORTION OF CYTOKINES AFTER MEDICATION IN MDR-TB PATIENTS WITH OR WITHOUT HIV

Figure 3. The following are the second line anti TB medication, the Th1/Th2 proportion of cytokines in MDR-TB patients is indicated. In the figure above box, plots are indicated with straight lines showing middle levels of MDR-TB patients and the underneath and top boundaries of every box indicate the 25th and 75th percentage, accordingly. The proportion of Th1/Th2 cytokines (IPN- γ /IFN- γ /IL-4, IL-12/IL-4, IL-12/IL-10) of MDR-TB patients without HIV ahead of medication (undyed bars), MDR-TB patients with HIV following medication (pearly bars) and MDR-TB patients with HIV following medication (vexed bars). The non-parametric Mann-Whitney test was applied to compute all the data with p values showing notable variation following the change of data to Log10 values.

Horizontal lines point out the median of MDR-TB without HIV (packed circles) and MDR-TB with HIV (Unlocked circles).

Uninduced serum specimens from MDR-TB patients with HIV (n=92) and MDR-TB patients without HIV (n=106) were assessed by Multiplex Cytokines. Investigation of data done by application of non-parametric Mann Whitney test with p-value showing notable variation following the change of data to Log10 values.

Figure 2 uninduced serum specimens from MDR-TB patients without HIV medication and following medication n=106 and MDR-TB patients with HIV hitherto medication and following medication n=92 was assessed by multiplex cytokine analysis. Investigation of data done by the application of non-parametric Mann Whitney test with p-value showing notable variation following the change of data to Log10 values. $p < 0.01$.

In the figure above the box, plots are indicated with straight lines showing middle levels of MDR-TB patients and the underneath and top boundaries of every box indicate the 25th and 75th percentage, accordingly. The proportion of Th1/Th2 cytokines (IPN- γ /IFN- γ /IL-4, IL-12/IL-4, IL-12/IL-10) of MDR-TB patients without HIV ahead of medication (undyed bars), MDR-TB patients with HIV following medication (pearly bars) and MDR-TB patients with HIV following medication (vexed bars). The non-parametric Mann-Whitney test was applied to compute all the data with p values showing notable variation following the change of data to Log10 values.

DISCUSSION

Few studies have compared the cytokine profiles of MDR-TB patients with or without HIV by application of Luminex technology. In this study, we contrasted the inflammatory mediator reactions within MDR-TB patients with HIV and MDR-TB patients without HIV utilizing serum. Assessing serum has shown prospects, hence the study points out variations in serum levels of cytokines in MDR-TB patients with and without HIV ahead of medication and following second line anti TB drug medication that potentially plays a role in the protection or development of MDR-TB. We assessed the serum level of pro-inflammatory mediators (TNF and IFN- γ , IL12 (p40), Anti-inflammatory mediators (IL-10 and IL-4), Growth factors (EGF and VEGF), and fractalkine and Chemokines mediators (IP-10, MCP-1, MCP-3, MIP-1 β). The most important findings of this study showed that MDR-TB with HIV alone do not give the impression to affect the mid serum level of any of the cytokine/chemokine mediators in MDR-TB patients and there was no statistically notable variation among MDR-TB with HIV and MDR-TB patients without HIV; also the serum level of IL-4, IFN- γ , MCP-3 IP-10, and MIP-1 β notably was altered following completion of intensive

phase of six months of second-line anti-TB medication in MDR-TB patients without HIV while in MDR-TB patients with HIV nothing of the cytokines and chemokines indicated notable variation following six months of second-line anti TB plus ARV drugs medication. The proportion of IFN- γ /IL-10 and IFN- γ /IL-4 were statistically dissimilar ($p < 0.01$) in MDR-TB patients HIV without following medication; and the proportion of Th1/Th2 cytokines mediators in MDR-TB patients with HIV was not altered following medication and it was notably diminished than MDR-TB patients without HIV following second line anti TB medication. More researchers that have investigated alteration in serum cytokines over numerous occasions following TB medication commencement have documented unnotable change all over the medication course (Lee JH, 2003; Sharma et al., 2016). In infections, involving TB, levels of anti-inflammatory cytokines mediators are always noted to be diminished.

At the starting point, MDR-TB patients with HIV presented a related serum cytokine level when contrasted with MDR-TB patients without HIV. This could be due to both MDR-TB and HIV infection inducing immune activation in a related design or because of the environment of HIV positive participants in this study where the majority of them were at less advanced HIV infection stage as confirmed by their CD4 counts. The consistent outcome was documented in other studies (Xiong et al., 2016; Martino et al., 2019). Several studies have shown that both MDR-TB and HIV co-infection can inhibit T cell effectors function, such as the production of IFN- γ and interleukin-2, and co-infection is associated with more reflective inhibition of type-1 cytokine reaction (Sokoya et al., 2017). Assessment of the serum cytokines profile indicated that out of the 106 cytokines assessed patients, the serum level of IFN- γ , IL-4, IP-10, MCP-3, and MIP-1 β was notably altered following intensive completion of second-line anti-TB medication in MDR-TB patients without HIV while in MDR-TB patients with HIV none of the cytokines and chemokines revealed notable variation following second line anti TB therapy. IFN- γ is the major cytokine concerned in the immune reaction in opposition to mycobacteria, and its major role is the arousal of macrophages to permit them to display its microbicidal role task (Khan et al., 2016). Compelling at the same time on our data proposing that the medicament of patients with imperfect acceptance to MDR-TB therapy possibly are required to incorporate IFN- γ as adjuvant therapy following complete characterization of the immunopathologic process in these and extra MDR-TB patients.

The mid serum level of IP-10 and IL-4 was notably diminished while the level of MCP-3 MIP-1 β and IFN- γ notably elevated following medication due to IFN- γ which is a pro-inflammatory mediator, IFN- γ is principally produced by activated Th1 cells, that drive to macrophage activation, eliminating *M. tuberculosis* in the

cell, and strengthened appearance of MHC II molecules to develop antigen recognition (Clute et al., 2013) and IL-4 is an anti-inflammatory mediator, it is logical to suggest that the elevated concentration of IFN- γ mediator and the diminished concentration of IL-4 could be because of the dispensation of the vigorously increasing bacteria and resolution of the infection following successful anti-TB therapy.

In *M. tuberculosis* infection some chemokines, such as MIP-1 β and IP-10, MCP-1 have the probable chance to enlist and trigger white blood cell production (Hasan et al., 2009; Monin L, 2014). MCP-1 mediates inflammation by regulating the migration and recruitment of monocytes in response to *M. tuberculosis* infection and is produced by pulmonary alveolar epithelial cells (Lin Y, Zhang M, 1998). The reduction of IP-10 and addition of MCP-1 and MIP-1 β following medication has been reported by other studies (Azzurri et al., 2005; Siawaya et al., 2009; Peresi et al., 2013). Trafficking of monocytes and activation of Th1 cells in the performance of IP-10 which results in inflamed foci, hence the reduction of IP-10 could be due to the resolution of inflammation as a result of anti-TB medication (Mihret et al., 2014).

The key role of MCP-1 and MIP-1b is to control the infection by attracting cells to the granuloma (Grzegorzewska and Mostowska, 2017). The level of cytokines and chemokines assessed in MDR-TB patients with HIV was not altered and this could be due to the inflammatory immune response in progress. The proportion of Th1/Th2 in MDR-TB patients with or without HIV displayed no variation ahead of medication while the proportion of IFN- γ /IL-10 and IFN- γ /IL-4 displayed a notable ahead of medication following medication in MDR-TB patients without HIV while none of the Th1/Th2 mediators' proportion displayed a notable variation following medication in MDR-TB patients with HIV. The proportion of Th1/Th2 mediators in MDR-TB patients with HIV was diminished than MDR-TB patients without HIV. The elevated level of IFN- γ /IL-10 and IFN- γ /IL-4 in MDR-TB patients without HIV is likely while a Th1 type immune reaction control following sanction of the energetic increasing bacteria and resolution of the infection by the anti-TB medication. Th1 cells have been revealed to give protection to TB by excreting IFN- γ and triggering antimycobacterial undertaking in macrophages. (Lyadova and Panteleev., 2016).

In this study, the second line anti TB therapy in MDR-TB patients did not alter the level of circulatory mediators. There are Some studies which had rev dissimilar results they reported that MDR-TB medication has an increasing effect on CD4 T cell count among individuals with MDR-TB/HIV co- infection (Sokoya et al., 2017; Desalegn et al., 2019), while other studies` report was consistent with our study, hence they observed no alteration in absolute CD4 T cell count or rehabilitation of the naive T cell population (Umanah et al., 2015). The diminished proportion of IFN- γ /IL-10 and IFN- γ /IL-4 following anti TB therapy in MDR-

TB patients with HIV is up to immune overtiredness by HIV co-infection with a probability of upcoming occurrence of MDR-TB in HIV-infected patients during down-regulation of IL-12 and IFN- γ up-regulation of IL-10 and IL-4.

Other researchers proposed that the elevated level of IL-10 is mainly established in chronic HIV infection (Kwon et al., 2012; Mikhael et al: 2018). Diminished manufacturer of IL-12 through peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMC) in reaction owing to MDR-TB antigens and diminished levels in cooperation of Th1 and Th2 mediators by PBMC match up with improved sensitivity and occurrence of MDR-TB in HIV-infected patients and may be responsible for their improved sensitivity (Bordon et al, 2011).

An increased infection severity in HIV positive patients could be due to a minimized proportion of IFN- γ /IL-4 (Basingnaa et al., 2018; Mikhael M. Averbakh and Atadzhan Ergeshow : 2018).

CONCLUSIONS

MDR-TB patients and MDR-TB with HIV infection present comparable serum cytokine and chemokine design. Moreover, second-line anti TB treatment significantly improves the level of cytokines and chemokines but does not re-establish the immune response in MDR-TB with HIV infection.

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Competing Interests

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

Availability of data and materials

The dataset used and/or analysed used in this study are available from the corresponding author on request.

Author Contributions

Conceived and designed the experiments: JCM & JOC. Performed the experiments: JCM. Analyzed the data: JCM, JOC and OSM. Contributed reagents/ materials/ analysis tools: JCM. Wrote the paper: JCM, JOC, HHS and BN

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